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D2.2 Mid-term Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Good practices for Research Software Development

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Abstract

This deliverable highlights the critical role of software quality in enhancing scientific research reliability within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) framework. By analysing current practices and creating the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQkit), it provides actionable guidelines to improve software robustness, reproducibility, and FAIR compliance across research domains.

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Statement of originality

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides a mid-term report on the EVERSE knowledge hub delivery. This knowledge hub, the Research Software Quality Kit ([RSQKit](#)), is designed to contain a collection of tools and guidelines on research software quality that align, adapt, and extend to the specific needs of various research communities.

In the RSQKit, we integrate the outcomes from various EVERSE work packages. Using concise descriptions of research software quality related tasks, we connect good practices collected by WP2 with software quality tools collected by WP3 and the training materials collected by WP5. The information collected on RSQKit is then evaluated by WP4 in domain specific use cases in the EOSC Science clusters. Feedback from this evaluation is then used to improve and extend the materials on RSQKit accordingly.

In this document, we provide a mid-term overview of the status of RSQKit. We briefly describe the process leading up to the current version of the RSQKit, and the type of content which is currently collected. We describe how content is contributed and curated, the role of the editorial board, and show how we use “research software stories” to illustrate the role of good practices in the EOSC Science clusters. We also explain the technical infrastructure needed to implement the RSQKit itself.

Since the initial release of RSQKit, there have been three new releases that both add a significant amount of content and improve the software infrastructure and capabilities of the RSQKit itself. We report on a selection of those improvements here as well.

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides a mid-term report on the EVERSE knowledge hub delivery. This knowledge hub, also known as the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit), is designed to contain a collection of tools and guidelines on research software quality that align, adapt, and extend to the specific needs of various research communities.

RSQKit integrates outcomes from various EVERSE work packages, such as the good practices collected by WP2 [1], [2], software quality tools collected by WP3 in TechRadar [3] and the training materials collected by WP5 [4]. In RSQKit, these collected resources are combined into concise descriptions of research software quality related tasks.

The information collected on RSQKit is evaluated by WP4 in domain specific use cases in the EOSC Science clusters [5]. Based on the feedback of this evaluation, the materials in the RSQKit are extended and improved accordingly.

The initial release of RSQKit was described in [6]. Since then, there have been three [new releases](#) of RSQKit that both add a significant amount of content and improve the software infrastructure and capabilities of the RSQKit itself. We have improved the contribution guidelines, set up a process and technical infrastructure to include tools, quality dimensions/indicators and training materials, and extended the editorial board. We will discuss these developments in more detail in this deliverable.

2. Knowledge Hub Processes

This section describes how the RSQKit is built from a content point of view. How and where do we collect good practices? How do we curate our collection to make sure it is easily accessible and has a meaningful impact on our intended audiences? And what do we do to build a community around the RSQKit, while connecting and aligning with existing efforts?

2.1. Initial collection of good practices

As explained in D2.1 [1], our collection of good practices followed a staged approach, starting out with a broad survey among project members and building on the expertise of the project members. The survey was completed by 28 participants, providing insights into how quality practices are perceived and applied across different types of research software. Respondents largely answered from a personal perspective, reflecting hesitation to speak on behalf of their research communities, though the range of disciplines represented was broad, spanning Library and Information Sciences, Bioinformatics, Astronomy, and Computer Science. Most participants identified as software practitioners, followed by research software managers and group representatives, with representation across all EOSC Science clusters.

The three-tier model of software types—analysis code, prototype tools, and research software infrastructure, as shown in Figure 8, was broadly accepted. Among these, research software infrastructure was rated as most important, followed by analysis code and then prototype tools. Quality practices were found to be most consistently applied to infrastructure software, with far less emphasis placed on prototypes and analysis code.

The main incentives for applying software quality practices were linked to funding opportunities, increasing FAIRness, and enhancing the overall impact of software. Both internal motivations, such as improving team workflows, and external drivers, such as community expectations and funder requirements, played a role.

When asked about quality dimensions, respondents prioritized accuracy of outputs for both performance and security considerations. Ethical aspects such as openness, provenance, and transparency were also highly valued. Applying a license was regarded as one of the most relevant steps in ensuring quality, while version control—particularly Git—was seen as essential and universally practiced. Continuous integration methods were also widely adopted, primarily through GitHub and GitLab workflows. Testing frameworks, including [pytest](#), [Google Test](#), and [CTest](#), were reported, along with benchmarking and static analysis tools.

Documentation emerged as a key area of tension. While participants recognized its importance, it was often underprioritized in practice, with many teams relying instead on scientific publications as a form of documentation. Tools like [Sphinx](#), [Read the Docs](#), [Jupyter Notebooks](#), and standards such as [CodeMeta](#) were mentioned, but adoption was less consistent than for version control and testing practices.

A recurring challenge identified in the survey was sustainability. Respondents highlighted a lack of financial support for long-term maintenance, quality assurance, and permanent research software engineer positions. Available funding was reported to focus heavily on initial development rather than ongoing maintenance and archiving. Infrastructure resources such as GitHub, GitLab, Zenodo, and Software Heritage were considered essential to bridging these gaps, while organizations like the Netherlands eScience Center were noted for providing valuable development support.

Community engagement was also identified as a factor in promoting quality practices. Co-creation with stakeholders, training and tutorials, open science advocacy, and mechanisms for community contributions (such as pull requests and open issue tracking) were seen as effective ways of embedding quality into research software projects.

While the survey's limited participation constrains its statistical weight, the findings offer useful indicators of broader trends. The results highlight both strengths—such as widespread adoption of version control and CI/CD—and weaknesses, particularly in funding for sustainability and the consistent use of documentation. The survey has produced a valuable collection of references, guidelines, and quality indicators, contributing to the EVERSE initiative and laying the groundwork for follow-up surveys to deepen understanding of specific aspects of research software quality.

2.2. RSQKit design journey

The goal of the RSQKit is to make good practices for research software development accessible and relevant to users, regardless of their background or expertise. The organization of our knowledge hub hence follows the four main “views” we think are most important for connecting with the research world. In addition, we identified a broadly felt need for a systematic characterization of what “quality” means for research software. We are designing a system of quality dimensions and indicators for this purpose. In this section we briefly highlight these organizational principles. For more information, please read the EVERSE Reference Framework [Chue2025].

2.2.1. Four views

The first view categorized software by maturity, technology readiness level or general applicability. This is summarized into the **three-tier model** illustrated in Figure 8 [Section 4.4](#). As this model shows, there is an abundance of analysis codes which generally starts with a single purpose, very small user base, and a focus on quick (often) one-off scientific results, which obviates the need for many software good practices like maintainability, complex design, performance optimization, and so on. Research software infrastructure is less common, has taken more time and considerations to develop, is more generally applicable and often has a large user and developer base, thus requiring a high technical readiness level. To support this, dedicated pages were created for tasks related to research software development, sharing, deployment, and maintenance. These resources are designed to guide users in addressing challenges regardless of where their work falls within the three-tier model.

The second view focusses in the Research Software Lifecycle model that describes the **development stages** at which a researcher might find themselves. This life cycle diagram is show in Figure 7 [Section 4.4](#). Briefly, it shows the interaction between the software development cycle and the parts of the research cycle related to the use of this software. This diagram is based on previous work done in [7]. In [Section 4.4](#) we will explain in more detail how this diagram was improved for use in the RSQKit.

The third view focusses on the research **domain**, in our case represented by the five EOSC Research Clusters. On RSQkit, each research cluster has its own page, providing information and listing services specific to that cluster. In addition, the RSQKit features Research Software Stories, which describe research cluster specific uses cases in detail. An example of such a research software story is described in [Section 4.2](#).

Finally, the fourth view focusses on the **personas**, the users’ roles in the research process. We currently have identified the following personas on the RSQKit:

- *Research Software Engineers*: someone who’s main focus is to develop research software.
- *Researcher who codes*: researchers that need to write or use (install, examples, use) code as part of their research
- *Principal investigator*: project leads who are required to write a Software Management Plans (SMP) for the software produced within their project.
- *Policy makers*: who need to know if the developers from the projects follow the good practices or which projects were funded and their compliance with FAIR.
- *Trainers*: who deliver training courses for researchers or RSEs on research software quality.

Additional personas may be added in the future, for example representing software stewards or infrastructure providers.

2.2.2 Representing Quality Dimensions and Indicators in EVERSE

In EVERSE, research software quality is defined as the degree to which software supports reliable, efficient, maintainable, and trustworthy research. [Research Quality dimensions](#) represent criteria relevant for assessing software quality (e.g., performance, maintainability, usability, robustness, etc.), while Research Software Indicators represent a specific aspect of software that can be measured. An example is shown in Figure 1, where the indicator “Software has descriptive metadata” belongs to the quality dimension “FAIRness”. Each software indicator belongs to a quality dimension.

Figure 1: An overview of how research quality indicators are linked to quality dimensions, using an example described in the Research Software Metadata Guidelines ([RSMD](#))

Both [indicators](#) and [dimensions](#) are described in a human-readable and machine-readable format, following a concrete schema that reuses existing standards like Schema.org and the W3C Data Quality Vocabulary.

2.3. Curation and harmonisation of good practices and tools

Within EVERSE two task forces have been set up to coordinate the efforts of the different work packages that provide input to the RSQKit. Next to the good practices provided by WP2, a tooling survey is provided by WP3 via TechRadar [3] and WP5 provides training materials via their training registry [4]. These task forces regularly publish updated versions of the EVERSE Reference Framework document in which we harmonize our knowledge [8].

While curation and harmonization of gathered good practices is envisaged to become a community effort, this task is currently being performed by the RSQKit Editorial board, as explained in more details in [Section 2.2.1](#) below.

Harmonization is an ongoing process that involves both proactive monitoring by the Editorial Board (e.g. [RSQKit_issue346](#) addresses harmonizing nomenclature, while [RSQKit_issue426](#) discusses how to deal with overlap in topics) input from community members who may notice discrepancies. Giving proper credit for contributors of all pages is an example of an issue on a more technical level, requiring modifications in the website backend (e.g. for pages versus tasks as in [RSQKit_issue435](#)).

In the bootstrapping phase, we have mainly depended on informal methods of gathering and curating insights from the leading European experts on research software. To make sure that RSQKit is sustainable in the long term (even after the EVERSE project ends), it is essential to reach out to the European research software community and get them involved in adding, maintaining and curating of RSQKit content.

As a first step in this direction, a [RSQKit hackathon](#) was held at the German RSE association's yearly conference [deRSECon25](#). Participants were introduced to the RSQKit and actively started contributing. We also connected with parallel software quality efforts within partner communities, notably by synchronizing with ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 [9]. Within EOSC, Opportunity Area 7 on Research Software is co-organized by EVERSE and has appointed many EVERSE members in the various work groups. Through this forum we can expect to harmonize good practices across an even broader community, reaching out even beyond Europe.

Based on our experience in working with these different communities, we will further improve our contribution guidelines to provide a concise set of underlying principles that people can use to write new content and to assess contributions from the editorial point of view. All of this to make sure that our processes are well documented for when new people need to be onboarded.

In the next stage of the project there will be further documentation, cross-pollination, use and identification of training needs in the EOSC science clusters led by WP4 and other research communities. The RSQKit will play a key role as the focal point for both disseminating those good practices that the community finds essential, and for providing a reference point for discussion on said practices.

2.3.1. Editorial Board

The editorial board now consists of 11 members of the EVERSE project that represent WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 – all EOSC Science Clusters are represented on the Editorial Board (ENVRI, ESCAPE, PANOSC and LSRI (via ELIXIR)) apart from SSH which is a future objective.

The responsibilities of the Editorial Board are:

- Careful review of proposed topics to ensure relevance to RSQKit.
- Work together with contributors to identify where and how and their contribution fits best in RSQKit.
- Before approving changes to RSQKit content, go through the Editors Checklist to make sure all conditions are met.
- Provide timely feedback for improving the quality of the content, according to the RSQKit Metadata Guidelines and Page Style Guidelines.

- Formatting content according to RSQKit templates.
- Join the weekly Editorial Board meeting.
- Maintain the RSQKit GitHub repository.

[Editorial board information](#) is publicly available in the RSQKit, this page includes information about how to join to the Editorial Board. The [editors' checklist](#) is publicly available, showing what editors review before approving content—improving RSQKit's contribution transparency.

2.3.2. Contributors

Contributors are essential to ensure the completeness and quality of the RSQKit content, at the time of submitting this deliverable, we have a total of 39 contributors this is up from 7 contributors at the time of submitting the earlier D2.1 [1].

Recognising those who have contributed to the content of RSQKit is essential. Therefore, the list of contributors [is publicly available in the RSQKit](#). Additionally, at the end of each page, the names of those who contributed specifically to that content are listed, allowing for recognition at both the global and page-specific levels.

To facilitate the contribution process, the following information about the process and quality control has been defined and publicly available at the [Get involved Section](#):

- [Contribution guidelines](#)
- [Metadata guidelines](#) to ensure the findability of the RSQKit elements. The Editorial Board defined metadata for the following elements:
 - **Contributor:** the list of contributors is defined in the [contributors file](#) .
 - **Affiliation:** the list of contributors' affiliations is defined in the [affiliations file](#).
 - **Page:** essential to allow the generation of page links, placing pages in the right section and connections with quality dimensions & indicators and training.
 - **Tools and resources:** The list of tools and resources are defined in the [tool and resource data file](#).
 - **Software quality indicator:** The list of indicators is in the [quality indicators data file](#).
 - **Software quality dimension:** Research Software Quality indicators can be grouped according to common categories or quality dimensions; the description of those dimensions is included in the [quality dimensions data file](#).
- [Page Style Guidelines](#) include valuable information to maintain consistency across the RSQKit we provide a style guide that defines the overall look and feel, including visual design, tone of communication, and formatting standards. This ensures that all content is presented in a coherent and consistent manner.
- Templates for multi-page sections ensure consistent info (roles, tasks, software stories, etc.). For those sections, the Editorial board has provided concrete templates (Markdown files), the list of templates is publicly available in the *Page Style Guidelines* page and template files are available at GitHub (in the corresponding section folder).
 - [Research Cluster or Infrastructure page template](#) for pages describing research clusters or infrastructures where software is a core part of activities.
 - [Research Software Story template](#) for pages listing specific pieces of research software and the quality steps they use.
 - [Role page template](#) for pages documenting different research professional roles and their relationship with research software.
 - [Task page template](#) for pages addressing common issues or describing commonly performed tasks around research software quality. This is the most common page type in RSQKit.

3. Technical implementation and management

The content of the RSQKit is the focus of the Editorial Board. However, the Editorial Board also acts as the Infrastructure Board for RSQKit. The technical implementation of the website and adaptations from the [ELIXIR Toolkit Theme \(ETT\)](#), a powerful template that allows connections and linkage and building up of the knowledge resource, e.g. linking tools and tasks is not trivial. A key feature of this template, and one of the reasons it was selected, is its ability to incorporate good practices organized into categories. It also automatically generates a summary table at the end of each page, listing all tools and resources mentioned. In this section, we briefly touch upon the way the “Infrastructure Board” manages the technical implementation.

3.1. Design, implement and deliver RSQKit

There are a few different technical infrastructure aspects of the RSQKit that needed to be dealt with the source of information.

- The primary source of tools is TechRadar. In addition, RSQKit includes tools not listed in TechRadar but referenced in its guidelines, as they provide context—such as certain programming languages or concepts—rather than being research software tools in the strict sense. We built an automated mechanism for loading TechRadar tools into RSQKit while differentiating them from the RSQKit ones to allow us to compare descriptive data (as they were originally developed in parallel) and allow us to synchronise, as well as keep track of item’s provenance for possible future maintenance.
- For quality dimensions and indicators, again these are imported into RSQKit from the working being done in other parts of EVERSE in WP2 and WP3.
- How training information is queried (training material is being stored in an EVERSE CERN based TeSS training portal instance which was setup and loaded as part of WP5) - the page metadata, query mechanism and page displays were all engineered to be easy to update and appear seamless and extensible if other training catalogues were added.
- The landing page was re-engineered to be more engaging and similar to the [RDMkit](#) (the Research Data Management kit that RSQKit is inspired by).
- When a Pull Request is done in GitHub there is infrastructure setup to create a running instance of the site so it’s much easier to review.
- There are tools that help to check for dead external links.

There is future work here that includes a dynamic research software lifecycle that connects to different parts of the website, the creation of task/tool assemblies that guide the user into how to get higher order tasks done, a dynamic page linking software quality dimensions and associated pages and being able to credit all contributors for all pages not just task pages.

As you can see while RSQKit is under active development and gaining new content as part of the EVERSE project – infrastructure developments follow hand in hand.

3.2. Accessibility and usability

A major concern for any knowledge base should be to periodically check whether your intended audience is indeed receiving what you intended them to receive, and can they find what they are looking for?

At the March 2024 EVERSE General Assembly Meeting in Barcelona, in the session on the RSQKit, an informal questionnaire was held to get an idea of what work still needs to be done – and these were the most important content types identified in Figure 2 and Figure 3:

Figure 2: Most important content types in RSQKit

And what the most important connections are between information.

Figure 3: Connections/ interlinking with RSQKit

There was focus since then until now on:

- Adding more task pages to build the knowledge base.
- Linking tools to tasks and improving descriptive metadata of tools (working with WP2 and WP3).
- Linking tasks with the appropriate training via working with WP5 [4].

Since the GAM survey there was further emphasis from the usability perspective on the “user journey” and how this related to the lifecycle of research and software – the output from this are further described in [Section 4.4](#), where we worked on the accessibility of one of our main “views”: the Research Software Lifecycle.

Usability is a topic which we gather comments on when doing outreach of RSQKit and there is further work scheduled around navigation, ordering and linkage to improve this in RSQKit. RSQKit is based on the ETT and RSQKit will benefit from updates in ETT as well as requirements and improvements from the RSQKit side being fed back to ETT.

3.3. RSQKit website updates

Since the last deliverable D2.1 [1] the RSQKit website has seen several updates and changes. For instance, the first version of the RSQKit, released in February 2025, included 14 pages distributed into 5 sections. The last version released before the submission of this deliverable was in July 2025 (v1.2.0) and included a total of 47 pages distributed into 7 sections.

We give an overview of the 7 sections in the appendix to this report. Here we summarize the main changes since D2.1, leaving out for brevity many more assorted minor updates:

- **Content and Structure:**
 - Added the first Research Software Stories from the ESCAPE cluster.
 - Added new task pages on CI/CD, software metadata and identifiers, code reviewing and computational workflows.
 - Added new role pages, e.g. researchers who code and principal investigators.
 - Research Software Lifecycle graphic and text revisited completely (see Section 4.4).
 - Task pages are now annotated with training information (see Section 4.5).
- **UI and design:**
 - Landing page redesigned
 - Navigation and Research Software Quality pages redesigned.
 - RSQKit logo designed, and colour scheme consistently applied throughout.
 - Updated icons to be freely available under permissive licences.
- **Technical:**
 - Automated synchronization of tools from TechRadar added.
 - Added visitor statistics using Matomo.
 - Added an automated broken link checker.
 - Added support for local installation of RSQKit via a Docker image.

4. Results

Having described above the processes that govern and have led to the delivery of our knowledge hub so far, it is now time to present the ways in which EVERSE aims to share those research software good practices it set out to do.

Instead of duplicating the contents of the entire RSQKit in this report, we highlight in the rest of this section five representative examples of the types of knowledge that have been delivered so far and the ways in which they are organized and integrated with other content:

1. **Research Software Tasks:** pages that contain knowledge on a good practice that was deemed of high priority by the EVERSE expert community.
2. **Research Software Stories:** real-life narratives of the role software quality plays within the EOSC Science clusters.
3. **Software Quality Indicators:** besides practical advice, we aim to provide the community with a systematic way to assess research software quality. Our Indicators provide a bridge between tools and good practices as well as a structured representation of research software quality in its full breadth.
4. **Research Software Lifecycle:** a representation of the stages under which Research Software goes through its life cycle.
5. **Integration of Training Resources:** the training materials collected in WP5 should also be easily findable at the right places in RSQKit.

4.1. Example of a Research Software Task: CI/CD

One of the most transformative tools of the past years for research software engineering has been the proliferation of free online tools that help you keep track of your software quality automatically. Most of these tools are run as part of what “continuous integration” (CI) and “continuous delivery/deployment” (CD) systems.

Without going into too much detail, CI/CD systems can be described as systems that monitor the code repository for changes and automatically run one or several scripts or pipelines. These pipelines can perform many tasks: check whether the code compiles, installs and runs correctly, run its test suite, keep track of performance over time, check whether the code adheres to style guidelines, package and publish the code to a repository, and more.

Using an online CI system contributes to software quality in at least two ways:

- It is helpful to the individual RSE or coder to make sure their code works as intended, not only on their own machine, but also in a standardized public environment.
- It tremendously facilitates collaboration. CI pipelines serve as a commonly agreed upon practical implementation of the quality standards in a project. It obviates the need for constant checks and discussion and helps garner trust between developers.

With these considerations in mind, since the last release, three pages were added on CI/CD:

- A [general overview page](#) on the topic of CI/CD
- Two more in-depth pages on how to put CI/CD to practice on the two major current repository platforms:
 - [Task automation using GitHub Actions](#)
 - [Task automation using GitLab CI/CD](#)

4.2. Example of Research Software Story: ACTS pilot project

The RSQKit now features Research Software Stories, including from the ESCAPE EOSC Cluster pilots. These illustrate good software quality processes and usage in a given research domain. This can be especially helpful to those who need to implement good software quality processes in their projects. In particular, they address the need for "How did you do this?" in the eyes of a researcher in a similar domain. As a result, the Research Software Stories cover all three tiers - research infrastructure, prototype tool, and analysis.

We illustrate in this section on the ACTS pilot [Research Software Story](#). Briefly, ACTS (which stands for *A Common Tracking Software*) is used by physicists across multiple teams, projects, and locations to track information captured during particle collisions. It is a large, mature project with thousands of files.

Figure 4: ACTS landing page

It is useful here to describe the process in which the stories were written:

- A skeleton for Research Software Stories was defined.
- Initial drafts were written based upon surveys of the ESCAPE pilots that had previously taken place for an earlier deliverable. In this case by a researcher from the ACTS team.
- The drafts were updated based upon presentations teams had given previously. While these drafts were detailed, they had very different styles and formats – due to being based on the content/style of the presentations which naturally varied.
- The style, grammar, and format were made consistent through the use of an LLM. This was provided with all three drafts and given a strict prompt that asked for style to be harmonised, and grammar fixed, but with as little change to the text as possible.

- This was helpful, but not the end of the process. The editor of the Research Software Stories then needed to edit for length, style, and importantly facts. This fact and correctness checking was important and necessary.
- Once this was done, the editor went back to the original members who had been surveyed and asked them to fact-check the stories. Again, in this case the same researcher from the ACTS team. By this stage, the changes that came back were largely small or involved the addition of extra references, which means this process worked quite well.
- The final step was the introduction of links across the RSQKit and beyond - ensuring that while each section is brief it has pointers to specific detail the reader is likely to need in response to the question "Yes, but how did you do that?"

The work for the research teams involved was minimal - a survey at the beginning and fact/link checking of the final, largely correct text. The strict control of the data going into the LLM and the requirement for "style consistency and grammar" limited the amount of creativity the LLM exercised with the content. The strict fact-checking by the editor before going back to the research team meant that the load for the researcher was likewise minimal. This was important given that, despite this low load, for one of the research stories this fact/link checking step by the researcher was an unavoidable delay point.

Lastly, the sections in the skeleton that were used for this iteration were:

- **The Problem:** Brief description of the domain the project sits in and the problem it addresses.
- **User Community:** Who uses the software and why.
- **Technical Aspects:** This covers language, architecture, and similar aspects
- **Libraries and Systems:** These covers libraries and systems the research software interacts with.
- **Software Quality Practices:** What core software practices the team uses, and links to how they do this.
- **Developer Community:** Who the developer community is, especially if/how it differs from the user community.
- **Tools:** The tools a team use can vary widely, along with how they apply them. The tools listed tend to focus on how the tools are applied at different stages of development (such as version control, build systems, etc.).
- **FAIR & Open:** How the project matches the FAIR criteria.
- **Documentation:** A description of the sort of documentation the team creates, how they create it, and how they maintain it (as appropriate).
- **Sustainability:** This tends to focus on how well the project is supported financially or practically - staff turnover, maturity, etc.
- **References :** Limited key references to core documentation and code, and anything else deemed important by the research software team involved (limited so people are not overwhelmed with where to start).

While each of the different tiers has very different requirements and answers for each of these sections, the format does make this clearer when comparing between research software

stories. It is therefore likely that a reader will find it easier to identify a project "similar to theirs" for practices they can learn from.

It has been noted after creating these Research Software Stories that it would likely be beneficial to state why and how the research software quality processes have benefitted and continue to benefit the projects. This is future work to be addressed and may help uncover which processes are essential and which are artefacts of survivorship bias in such projects.

4.3. Software Quality Indicators and Dimensions

In this section we describe how the Research Software quality model used in EVERSE enables linking the RSQKit with other key results of the project: the [TechRadar](#), the [Research Quality Pipelines](#) and the EVERSE Training catalogue [4].

4.3.1 Software quality dimensions

Below is a list of the currently adopted dimensions, agreed at the second EVERSE General Assembly Meeting and inspired by existing quality frameworks such as [ISO/IEC 25010](#) and principles such as FAIR4RS [10] We summarize them below:

- **Compatibility:** degree to which a product, system or component can exchange information with other products, systems or components, and/or perform its required functions while sharing the same common environment and resources.
- **FAIRness:** degree to which research software adheres to the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. These principles, adapted for research software, aim to enhance the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of software, thereby maximizing its value and impact in scientific research
- **Flexibility:** degree to which a product can be adapted to changes in its requirements, contexts of use or system environment.
- **Functional suitability:** characteristic that represents the degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions.
- **Interaction Capability:** degree to which a product or system can be interacted with by specified users to exchange information via the user interface to complete specific tasks in a variety of contexts of use.
- **Maintainability:** degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified to improve it, correct it or adapt it to changes in environment, and in requirements.
- **Performance Efficiency:** degree to which a product performs its functions within specified time and throughput parameters and is efficient in the use of resources (such as CPU, memory, storage, network devices, energy, materials...) under specified conditions.
- **Reliability:** degree to which a system, product or component performs specified functions under specified conditions for a specified period of time.
- **Safety:** degree to which a product under defined conditions avoids a state in which human life, health, property, or the environment is endangered.
- **Security:** degree to which a product or system defends against attack patterns by malicious actors and protects information and data so that persons or other products or systems have the degree of data access appropriate to their types and levels of authorization.

- **Sustainability:** capacity of the software to endure. In other words, sustainability means that the software will continue to be available in the future, on new platforms, meeting new needs.

This set of quality dimensions may grow in the future, as feedback is received from scientific communities adopting them. All [dimensions](#) are listed in EVERSE catalogue and a more detailed [description](#) of each dimension is also available in RSQKit.

4.3.2 Linking Software quality indicators in the RSQKit

Hundreds of software quality indicators have been defined in existing literature and good practices. Some of these indicators have been overviewed in state-of-the-art reports [11] while others are proposed by different communities or organizations (e.g., [Chaoss](#), [OpenSSF](#), etc.), or even informally (e.g., [JOSS guidelines for reviewers](#)). In EVERSE, together with the ELIXIR community, we conducted a series of hackathons to collect, characterize, and group indicators from seven canonical sources. The final report [12] included a review of more than 200 indicators, together with their feasibility (i.e., whether the participants considered them easy to automate or not).

Using this report as a reference, we have started importing existing indicators and linking them in task pages in the RSQKit. So far, we have a total of 25 software quality indicators. Our catalogue of indicators is available [online](#). Each indicator includes a human-readable and machine-readable description following the schemas referenced in [Section 4.3.1](#). The page “[Citing software](#)” includes a reference to the indicator “[software_has_citation](#)”, below is a code snippet showing how task pages are annotated with indicators in the page metadata.:

```
---
title: Citing software
description: How can people cite your software?
contributors: ["Jason Maassen"]
page_id: citing_software
indicators: [software_has_citation]
related_pages:
your_tasks: [software_identifiers, software_metadata]
keywords: ["citation", "cff"]
training:
  - name: "EVERSE TeSS"
    registry: TeSS
    url: "https://everse-training.app.cern.ch"
---
```

Snippet 1: RSQKit page metadata, including a reference to the research software quality indicator “software_has_citation”

Table 1 shows an overview of the current list of indicators, with their corresponding quality dimension. Out of 25 indicators, 19 of them (76%) address a single quality dimension. A total of 4 indicators address 2 quality dimensions (16%), and 2 indicators address 3 (8%). As shown in Table 1, FAIRness currently plays an important role in our current selection of indicators, as reflected in many of the good practices in the RSQKit. In the rest of the project, we will continue

to update the list of indicators to 1) provide a comprehensive quantitative analysis all quality dimensions and 2) to indicate how to assess Research Software quality in different tiers of the software life cycle.

Name	Quality Dimension
Software is archived in a scholarly repository	FAIRness
Software is archived in Software Heritage	FAIRness
CodeMeta completeness	FAIRness
Software has dependency management solution	Compatibility; Security; Sustainability
Software has descriptive metadata	FAIRness
Software has continuous integration tests	Maintainability
Software uses citation	FAIRness
Software has license	FAIRness
Software has no linting issues	FAIRness; Maintainability
Software is published as a downloadable package	Flexibility
Software has releases	Maintainability
Software requires human code review	Functional suitability
Software is listed in a registry	FAIRness
No critical vulnerabilities	Security
No leaked credentials	Security
Software has persistent and unique identifier	FAIRness
Software has ci/cd workflows in its repository	Maintainability
Software specifies requirements	FAIRness; Flexibility; Maintainability
Software has documentation	FAIRness; Interaction capability
Software provides tests.	FAIRness; Reliability
has static analysis for common vulnerabilities	Security
Software uses fuzzing	Safety
Software uses a tool for warnings or mistakes	FAIRness, Maintainability
Software makes use of version control	FAIRness
Software follows versioning standards	FAIRness

Table 1. Research Software quality indicators.

Figure 5 shows the number of indicators defined in each dimension. FAIRness is represented as the dimension with the highest number of indicators (15). In contrast, some dimensions, such as Functional Suitability, currently do not have any indicators.

4.3.3 Leveraging Software Quality Indicators to connect to other EVERSE outputs

Our knowledge hub uses the research software quality indicators (and the RSQKit) as the central gateway for connecting to other EVERSE outputs. Among them, we highlight the TechRadar which consists of a portal that gathers all relevant tools mentioned in RSQKit tasks and organizes them around the quality dimensions described in [Section 4.3.3](#). In addition, the [Research Software Quality pipelines](#) provide a framework for automatically assessing the quality of a research software project based on the tools of the Technology Radar while following the indicators of the task pages in the RSQKit. Finally, the [EVERSE Training portal](#) supports searching for existing training materials for each of the task pages of the RSQKit, as discussed in [Section 4.5](#).

4.4. Research Software Lifecycle

We began with an [initial lifecycle diagram](#) as presented in [7]. This diagram predates the EVERSE project, but was created by some of its partners in earlier work on framing and classifying research software (in a way similar and mimicking to the [data lifecycle from RDMkit](#)). The aim was to describe the different stages of research software development and, how these stages fit within the research lifecycle supported by that software (rather than research in general). RSQKit is then intended to provide a general description and introduction to each stage, highlight the main considerations to address at each point, and link to specific tasks, training materials, and other resources for further reading.

We identified several needs that were emergent from the interaction with the EOSC Science clusters that would be best reflected by creating a new visualisation based on the existing diagram that better reflected the interplay between the research life cycle and the software in research lifecycle as well as improving visual design and having something which was easier to link out from.

A new version of the diagram was produced after discussions at Software Sustainability's Institute's Collaborations Workshop CW25, with the goal of better representing the research software lifecycle. In this iteration, we identified three nested cycles: the outer research cycle, the software project cycle, and the inner software development iteration. Early discussions also pointed out the need to distinguish between lifecycle stages and software "states" (e.g., active, dormant, restarted).

Further refinement led us to conclude that three cycles were too complex and that some elements were out of scope. We ultimately settled on two (see Figure 7): the outer research cycle and the inner software engineering and development cycle, with a clear indication of where the inner cycle begins and which stages of the two cycles run in parallel.

Figure 7. Research Software Lifecycle

To improve the visualisation, we engaged a graphic designer, who produced several iterations of the diagram. These refinements also prompted discussions about where archiving and sunsetting software (e.g., via Software Heritage or Zenodo) should be represented, as the current version shows only a “steady state.”; incorporating this remains as future work.

We also considered the connection between the research software lifecycle and [the three-tier model of research software](#) (see Figure 8). This model provides a framework for understanding the diverse landscape of research software—from scripts, code, and notebooks to computational workflows, libraries, frameworks, utilities, and applications. It distinguishes three tiers based on purpose: analysis code, prototype tools, and research software infrastructure. While closely related, we decided not to include this model within the lifecycle diagram, as it is already explained in detail in the accompanying text and would have overcomplicated the diagram.

Figure 8. Three-tier model of research software.

The current state of the research software lifecycle diagram is stable but still open to discussion and refinements. It represents the outcome of iterative redesigns, extensive community feedback, and a careful balance between complexity and clarity—evolving from a simple cycle to a model that acknowledges the interplay of research and software processes,

while leaving space for future additions such as archiving and long-term software states. Most of the discussions and design iterations are documented in the [related GitHub issue](#).

4.5. Integration of Training and Tools Resources

The integration of RSQKit with the training resources collected in WP5 and stored in the [EVERSE TeSS training registry](#) takes place through RSQKit's task pages. Each task page is enriched with metadata, including a set of keywords that best describe its content. These keywords are then used to generate a TeSS search query, with the resulting matches displayed directly on the corresponding RSQKit task page. More details on this integration can be found in the WP5 deliverable *"D5.2 Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Good practices: Initial Release."*[4].

We plan to extend this mechanism to incorporate training and tool resources from other domain and research cluster services that support search queries—for example, training resources from [ENVRI Hub](#) and [SSHOC Marketplace](#), as well as tools pages from the EVERSE TechRadar.

5. Next Steps

As mentioned in [Section 3.2](#), users are always eager for more content, but also in particular for “guided improvements”, i.e., to help RSEs get to where they want to be in terms of software quality. We aim to work on tailored “user journeys” where the “views” help determine which practices, tools, training, or other materials are most valuable for them at that time.

The in-depth survey performed within EVERSE (see [Section 3.1](#)) is planned to be followed up with an updated version to be set out within the broader “EVERSE network”, i.e. the European community that EVERSE is building of all researchers interested in research software quality. By harnessing this community, we expect to tailor our knowledge base to the research communities’ needs even further. We foresee that, for instance, by more broadly disseminating ideas around different software tiers will help researchers to improve their software (and hence their research) in a more focused and efficient way.

The RSQKit itself will remain the focal point for EVERSE to gather and connect good practices, tools, indicators, training, and other resources and subsequently to disseminate it. We will keep updating our processes for collection and curation where needed. The Editorial Board needs to and thus will keep striving to include perspectives from all research clusters and types of stakeholders. Input and increasingly active involvement from the broader community (especially beyond EVERSE) will be crucial to making sure the long-term sustainability of the RSQKit is guaranteed. Based on our experience in working with these different communities, we will further improve our contribution guidelines to provide a concise set of underlying principles that people can use to write new content and to assess contributions from the editorial point of view. In addition, the Editorial Board, will put together a roadmap document to prioritize the task pages that are considered key additions from the feedback received so far, in order to complete the Knowledge Hub.

In the next stage of the project there will be further documentation, cross-pollination, use and identification of training needs in the EOSC science clusters led by WP4 and other research communities. The indicator list will continue to be refined and expanded, making each indicator more visible in their corresponding task pages in the RSQKit. We will refine and possibly expand the dimensions established in the initial survey and workshops and connect the dimensions to indicators in a balanced way, making sure that all dimensions can be translated to practical guidance for enhancing quality. Future iterations of the survey and RSQKit development will test these dimensions against real-world applications, ensuring they remain relevant and valuable to the scientific community. Finally, we expect RSQKit to play a key role as the focal point for both disseminating good practices that the community finds essential, and for providing a reference point for discussion on said practices.

RSQKit will strive to be a resource co-produced with input from the wider project, wider community (via the EVERSE Network) and beyond; we will be open, welcoming and improve our methods of crediting all types of contributions.

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Appendix: RSQKit website

The RSQKit is the knowledge hub containing a collection of tools and guidelines on research software quality that align, adapt, and extend to the specific needs of various research communities.

- The RSQKit is publicly available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/>
- The source code for the generating the content of the RSQKit is available at <https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit>

The version most recently released before the submission of this deliverable was in July 2025 (v1.2.0) including a total of 47 pages distributed into 7 sections described in the following sub-sections.

Figure 9 depicts the landing page; the main body of the page is a set of direct links to the sections. In the menu, at the top of the page, include options to access to the pages [About](#) and [Contact us](#), section [Get involved](#), links to the project social media sources and GitHub repository.

Figure 9. RSQKit landing page

This appendix provides an overview of the current content of the knowledge hub. Each of the following subsections corresponds to a section of the RSQKit. Two types of sections are available: single-page and multiple-page sections. A single-page section presents all related information on a single page, typically including a menu whose entries link to specific content within the page. Multiple-page sections, in contrast, consist of several pages, with their sub-

pages accessible through the sub-menu located on the left-hand side of the interface. All pages can include a menu on the right to go directly to specific content within the page.

- **Research Software section (improved)**

This section is a multi-page section covering general aspects of Research Software along four specific pages (see Figure 10).

- **What is research Software?** Including some definitions relate to Research Software (RE). Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/research_software#what-is-research-software.
- **Three-tier model** Description of the three-tier model to characterise the RE software maturity. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/three_tier_view.
- **Lifecycle** Description of the RE software development process phases. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/life_cycle.
- **Quality** (new) Including the definition of RS quality, the quality dimensions and indicators. Available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/quality>.

Figure 10. 'Research Software' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/research_software.

- **Quality dimensions & indicators section (improved version of the former Research Software Quality)**

This is a single-page section including the definition and assessment of research software quality a general introduction to Research Software Quality. The page includes the definition of eleven (four in v. 1.0) quality dimensions: Compatibility, Fairness, Flexibility, Functional suitability, Interaction capability, Maintainability, Performance efficiency, Reliability, Safety, Security, and Sustainability (see Figure 1).

Figure 11. 'Research Software Quality' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/rs_quality.

- **Research clusters & infrastructures section (improved version of the former Research communities)**

This section is a multi-page section listing the research clusters and infrastructures involved in the project (see Figure 12). The current version includes one page for each EOSC Research cluster, including the cluster goal and/or provided services:

- **ENVRI - environmental sciences** (new). Research cluster information available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/envri>.
- **ESCAPE - physics & astronomy**. Research cluster information available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/escape>.
- **LS-RI - life sciences** (new). Available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/ls-ri>.
- **PaNOSC - physics & astronomy**. Research cluster information available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/panosc>.
- **SSHOC - social sciences & humanities**. Research cluster information available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/sshoc>.

Figure 12. 'Research Clusters & Infrastructures' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/research_clusters_and_infrastructures.

- **Research Software Stories section (new)**

This is a multi-page section; each page describes a concrete research software story that corresponds to a concrete piece of research software and with a focus on the quality steps that they use use (see Figure 1). The current version includes three stories.

- **ACTS**. The ACTS project (Acts Common Tracking Software) was created to provide a single, experiment-independent toolkit for efficient track reconstruction. Story description available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/acts_research_software_story.
- **BALER**. It is a tool for Machine Learning Based Data Compression. Story description available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/baler_research_software_story.
- **xAODAnaHelpers (xAH)**. It is a common analysis framework widely used within the ATLAS experiment. Story available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/xah_research_software_story.

Figure 13: 'Research Software Stories' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/research_software_stories

- **Your role section (improved)**

This is a multi-page section; each page describes a concrete role played by research professionals. Complementing the role description, these pages include training resources and/or guidelines to support the tasks the role need to fulfil (see Figure 14). The current version includes five roles (one in v.1.1.0).

- **Researcher who codes.** Researchers who code are academics or research domain experts who write software or scripts as part of their research workflow. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/researcher_who_codes.
- **Research Software Engineer (RSE).** It is a software engineer developing software to support research. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/research_software_engineer.
- **Principal Investigator (PI).** Referring to principal investigator coordinating research project that includes software development. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/principal_investigator.
- **Policy maker.** Referring to a policy maker at a funding agency, research institution, or governmental body. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/policy_maker.
- **Trainer.** Referring to trainers delivering training courses in research software development and quality for specific research domain or in general. Available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/trainer>.

Figure 14. 'Your role' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/your_role.

- **Your tasks section (improved)**

This is a multi-page section; each page describes a specific task commonly encountered when working with research software. These pages provide detailed descriptions of the most frequent functional areas and challenges, offering practical solutions by explaining how to use existing tools and resources (see Figure 15). The current version includes 19 pages (seven in v.1.0).

- **Choosing languages, tools & infrastructures.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/languages_tools_infrastructures
- **Citing software.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/citing_software.
- **Computational workflows.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/computational_workflows.
- **Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery/Deployment.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/ci_cd.
- **Creating a good README.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/creating_good_readme.
- **Documenting software.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/documenting_software.
- **Documenting software using 'Read The Docs'.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/documenting_software_readthedocs.
- **Improving environmental sustainability.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/improving_environmental_sustainability.
- **Licensing software.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/licensing_software.
- **Organising software projects.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/organising_software_projects.
- **Packaging & releasing software.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/packaging_releasing_software.
- **Performing a code review.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/code_review.
- **Releasing software.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/releasing_software.
- **Reproducible software environments.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/reproducible_software_environments.
- **Software documentation.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/software_documentation.
- **Software identifiers.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/software_identifiers.
- **Software metadata.** Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/software_metadata.
- **Task automation using GitHub Actions.** Available at (https://everse.software/RSQKit/task_automation_github_actions).
- **Task automation using GitLab CI/CD** (https://everse.software/RSQKit/task_automation_gitlab_ci_cd).
- **Testing software** (https://everse.software/RSQKit/testing_software).
- **Using version control** (https://everse.software/RSQKit/using_version_control).
- **Writing readable code** (https://everse.software/RSQKit/writing_readable_code).

Figure 15. 'Your tasks' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/your_tasks

- **All tools and resources (new)**

This is a single-page section including the list of all the tools and resources related to the project (see Figure 16). The page contains a table including the name (and the link to the tool or resource), description, and the set of RSQKit related pages. The current version includes 144 tools and resources.

Figure 16. 'All tools and resources' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/all_tools_and_resources.

- **Get involved section (new)**

This is a multi-page section including the information related to contribute to the RSQKit. This section includes six specific pages (see Figure 17).

- **Contribution guidelines.** Including the details dedicated to the contributors. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/contribution_guidelines.
- **Metadata Guidelines.** Description for the metadata that should be used to describe some resources and pages. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/metadata_guidelines.
- **Page Style Guidelines.** Description of the style guidelines to ensure that all sections of the website follow a consistent design. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/page_style_guidelines.
- **Editorial Board.** Details of the Editorial Board members and how to join. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/editorial_board.
- **Editors Checklist.** Definition of the criteria that need to be verified before approving changes to the RSQKit. Available at https://everse.software/RSQKit/editors_checklist.
- **Contributors.** List of individuals contributing to the RSQKit. Available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/contributors>

Figure 17. 'Get involved' section in the RSQKit

Section available in the RSQKit at https://everse.software/RSQKit/get_involved